

Distinct electroencephalography biomarker for tinnitus

Jae Ok Hwang¹, Tae-Yaep Kim², Kuk-In Jang^{3*}, Pyong Woon Park^{3*}

¹ Mompyeonanhan Korea Medicine, Wonju, Republic of Korea

² Dondaemun INJE Korean Medicine, Seoul, Republic of Korea

³ Corporate Research Institute, Panaxtos Corp., Seoul, Republic of Korea

*** Corresponding Authors**

Kuk-In Jang Ph.D

Corporate Research Institute,

Panaxtos Corp., 3F Shindonga Tower, 33 Ogeum-ro 11-gil,

Songpa-gu, Seoul, 05543, Republic of Korea.

Tel: +82-10-2061-5223

E-mail: jcsamuel@panaxtos.com

Pyong Woon Park Ph.D

Corporate Research Institute,

Panaxtos Corp., 3F Shindonga Tower, 33 Ogeum-ro 11-gil,

Songpa-gu, Seoul, 05543, Republic of Korea.

Tel: +82-2-2051-1380

E-mail: panipara@panaxtos.com

Abstract

Background: Tinnitus is a serious neurological condition primarily attributed to abnormal auditory perception in the brain. Its symptoms include ringing, buzzing, and whistling sounds, with subjective tinnitus being the most common type. Despite its prevalence, the neurophysiological mechanisms underlying tinnitus remain unclear, and no definitive electroencephalography (EEG) biomarkers have been identified. This study aims to identify EEG biomarkers in patients suffering from subjective tinnitus who visited a traditional Korean medicine clinic.

Methods: The study recruited 2,309 patients suffering from subjective tinnitus and 2,371 age- and sex-matched normal controls. Wearable two-channel EEG was recorded for 3 minutes. Following a 40-second baseline stabilization period, EEG data were continuously recorded for 60 seconds with eyes closed and then for another 60 seconds with eyes open. Preprocessing steps were applied to remove artifacts. EEG frequency bands were decomposed into Delta, Theta, Alpha, Sensory Motor Rhythm (SMR), Low Beta, High Beta, and Gamma. Feature selection method, including recursive feature elimination with cross-validated support vector machine (RFECV-SVM), was used. Classification was conducted using SVM and Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM) methods.

Results: Compared to normal controls, patients with subjective tinnitus exhibited increased relative Delta and Theta activity and decreased High Beta and Gamma activity. In absolute power measures, patients showed reductions in Alpha and Low Beta activity. Additionally, patients demonstrated higher Theta/SMR, Theta/Low Beta, and Alpha/Low Beta ratios, along with a reduced Alpha/Theta ratio. Machine learning analysis revealed that SVM achieved the best classification performance, with a balanced accuracy of 0.59 and an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC-ROC) of 0.62.

Conclusion: This study highlights distinct EEG biomarkers in patients suffering from subjective tinnitus, offering insights into their neurophysiological mechanisms and providing a basis for classification models.

Keywords: Tinnitus, Electroencephalography, Machine learning

Introduction

Subjective tinnitus (ST) is a common brain disorder, with most patients reporting symptoms such as buzzing sounds and dizziness^{1,2}. Hypothetically, tinnitus could progress due to the interaction between the auditory system and the visual and peripheral nerves³. However, the pathological mechanisms remain unresolved. Since there is no consistent and comprehensive theory, several modalities for measuring ST have been explored⁴⁻⁷.

Pathophysiological changes in neural structures have been observed in the insula, occipital lobe, middle frontal gyrus, and parietal lobe⁸. Some patients with chronic ST showed a cervical spine dysfunction⁹. It is believed to be driven by mechanisms in the central nervous system, even if it initially results from peripheral auditory dysfunction^{10,11}. This is supported by findings that tinnitus often persists or worsens even after auditory nerve sectioning¹². Functional magnetic resonance image (MRI) study using resting-state BOLD signal has shown strong connectivity between the left somatosensory cortex and corresponding regions in the right hemisphere, suggesting widespread neural involvement¹³⁻¹⁵. Additionally, diffusion tensor imaging research has indicated structural changes in white matter pathways, such as the arcuate fasciculus, which connects auditory, frontal, and limbic regions, potentially contributing to tinnitus perception^{16,17}.

Electroencephalography (EEG) has been demonstrated as a measurable tool for ST¹⁸⁻²⁰. Spectral and current source changes in EEG were identified in patients with tinnitus²¹. Patients with ST showed changes in EEG microstates, compared to healthy individuals²⁰. Theta activity of resting-state in frontal area was increased in patients with severe chronic ST, compared to less severe ST¹⁹. Patients also showed increased delta, alpha, and gamma activity²². A study on classification using decision tree-based ensemble learning demonstrated that the proposed model, which utilized EEG network features and reduced data dimensions through principal component analysis, achieved 89% accuracy in distinguishing between patients with auditory disorders and normal controls²³. EEG is a strong functional measure that is low-cost and time-efficient. However, the studies mentioned above suffer from a limited sample size, often involving only dozens of participants. Small sample populations present several limitations, which can make it difficult to generalize the findings.

The present study explored EEG biomarkers differentiating patients and normal controls (NC), and invented machine learning (ML) model for ST screening. First, conventional statistical comparisons were conducted between patients with ST and NCs. Second, we proposed a classification model using ML.

Materials and Methods

Participants

Patients ($n = 2,309$; age = 56.57 ± 12.66 years; m/f = 993/1,316) with subjective tinnitus (ST) were recruited through a multi-center collaboration involving oriental medicine clinics in partnership with PANAXTOS Corp. Age- and sex-matched normal controls (NCs; $n = 2,371$; age = 56.46 ± 12.65 years; m/f = 998/1,373) were recruited through PANAXTOS Brain Centers across South Korea. All participants were native Koreans. There were no significant group differences in age or sex distribution ($\chi^2 = 0.527$; Table 1). ST diagnosis was based on patients' major complaints, including ringing, buzzing, roaring sounds, and tinnitus-related dizziness. Individuals with mood disorders, psychosis, cognitive impairment, or neurological conditions were excluded. Study procedures were displayed in Figure 1. This study analyzed retrospective, fully de-identified human data, which contained no personal identifiers and could not be linked to individual identities. Although the dataset included group-level demographic information (e.g., age and sex), no individual-level identification was possible.

Figure 1. Study procedures

EEG recording

The EEG recording was conducted in a sound-attenuated room, where participants were instructed to remain still with their eyes closed and open in a quiet environment. Data were collected over a period of 180 seconds, with alternating 40-second intervals of eyes-closed and eyes-open conditions using the Neuroharmony M2, a two-channel EEG device (PANAXTOS Co. Ltd, Seoul, South Korea). Gold-coated dry electrodes were attached to the prefrontal cortex at FP1 and FP2, with the reference electrode positioned on the left earlobe and the ground electrode at FPz. The signals were recorded at a sampling rate of 250 Hz. An independent expert, with no affiliation to the study, supervised the recording.

Quantitative EEG analysis

EEG signals were recorded at a sampling rate of 250 Hz and segmented into time windows for frequency-domain analysis. Each epoch had a duration of 250 milliseconds, and a total of 40 seconds of data were selected for further processing in each of the eyes-closed and eyes-open states. To extract frequency components, the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)

was applied²⁴. The analysis was performed on 40 non-overlapping 1-second segments, and the spectral values obtained from each segment were averaged to improve the stability and reliability of the frequency representation. The transformation of the time-domain EEG signal $g(t)$ into the frequency domain is mathematically expressed as follows:

$$c(f) = \Delta t \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} g(t) e^{-i2\pi km/N}$$

where $c(f)$ represents the transformed frequency-domain signal, Δt is the sampling interval ($\Delta t=1/250$ sec), $g(t)$ is the EEG signal in the time domain, N is the number of samples per segment (250 samples per second), k is the sample index, m represents the frequency component index, and $e^{-i2\pi km/N}$ is the complex exponential function for frequency transformation. By averaging the FFT results across segments, a spectral profile was obtained, allowing for the extraction of absolute and relative power within specific frequency bands. The frequency bands analyzed were Delta (0.1–3.9 Hz), Theta (4.0–7.9 Hz), Alpha (8.0–12.9 Hz), Sensory Motor Rhythm (SMR) (12.0–15.9 Hz), LowBeta (13.0–20.9 Hz), HighBeta (21.0–30.9 Hz), and Gamma (31.0–45.9 Hz). Basis on absolute values, Band-Ratio was calculated as Theta/SMR, Theta/LowBeta, Alpha/Theta, and Alpha/LowBeta.

Statistical analysis

Demographic characteristics, including age and sex, were compared between groups using a t-test and Pearson's chi-square test. EEG variables were compared between patients with ST and NCs through multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA). Statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.05$ with two-tailed. To account for multiple comparisons, the Bonferroni correction method was used.

Feature selection and classification

Feature Selection

Features were ranked and selected by recursive feature elimination cross-validation with support vector machine (RFECV-SVM)²⁵. We computed the RFECV-SVM-based feature importance for initially 72 features. Finally, the top 14 features were selected. RFECV iteratively removed the less important features using SVM with linear kernel. 5-folds cross-validation was applied to find optimal feature set.

Classification

The selected features are used to train two classification models: SVM and gradient boosting machine (GBM). Hyperparameter optimization is performed using grid search cross-validation. SVM was used with radial basis function (RBF) and linear kernels. Regularization parameters were set at 0.1, 1, 10, and 100. Grid search cross-validation was applied. Gamma values were 0.1 and 0.01. GBM was used to build a tree using estimator (100, 200, and 300), max depth (3, 4, and 5), learning rate (0.01 and 0.1), min split of samples (2 and 5), and subsample (0.8, 0.9, and 1.0).

Model Evaluation

To ensure robust evaluation, we employ 5-fold stratified cross-validation. The dataset is split into five subsets, where four are used for training and one for validation, repeated across all folds. Final results included the best hyperparameters for SVM and GBM, and performance scores based on multiple evaluation metrics. This methodology provides an optimized framework for classification, ensuring improved model performance and reliability. Evaluation metrics were used with balanced accuracy, F1 score, precision, sensitivity, specificity, and area under the curve - receiver operating characteristic (AUC-ROC). Main result was reported as balanced accuracy, which is suitable for imbalanced dataset. Balanced accuracy is the average of sensitivity (recall or true positive rate) and specificity (true negative rate). It compensates for class imbalance by equally weighing the accuracy of both positive and negative classes (True Positive (TP), True Negative (TN), False Positive (FP), and False Negative (FN)).

$$\text{Balanced accuracy} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{TP}{TP+FN} + \frac{TN}{TN+FP} \right)$$

Results

Demographic and statistical results were presented in Table 1. The age and sex variables did not significantly differ between patients with ST and NCs.

Table 1. Demographic and statistical results.

Variables		Normal(n=2,371)		Tinnitus(n=2,309)		f	Adjusted p	Original p
		mean	sd	mean	sd			
Demographics	Age	56.46	12.65	56.57	12.66		t=0.31, p=0.754	
	Sex(n, male/female)	998/1373		993/1316			$\chi^2=0.527$	
Absolute values Eyes-closed	Delta_Left	8.97	22.48	8.66	20.09	0.26	1.000	0.610
	Delta_Right	9.83	27.78	9.03	19.62	1.26	1.000	0.261
	Theta_Left	3.90	9.72	3.72	7.75	0.49	1.000	0.486
	Theta_Right	4.27	10.82	3.86	6.83	2.46	1.000	0.117
	Alpha_Left	3.54	7.83	2.90	5.60	10.10	0.108	0.001
	Alpha_Right	3.77	7.89	3.07	5.43	12.51	0.029	0.000
	SMR_Left	2.08	4.42	1.81	3.70	5.22	1.000	0.022
	SMR_Right	2.23	4.54	1.91	3.44	7.26	0.509	0.007
	LowBeta_Left	2.09	4.19	1.71	3.62	10.56	0.084	0.001
	LowBeta_Right	2.19	4.07	1.79	3.30	13.78	0.015	0.000
	HighBeta_Left	1.75	3.52	1.42	4.34	7.76	0.387	0.005
	HighBeta_Right	1.82	3.53	1.47	4.06	10.19	0.103	0.001
	Gamma_Left	1.76	4.48	1.21	6.13	12.33	0.032	0.000
	Gamma_Right	1.81	4.57	1.22	5.77	15.08	0.008	0.000
Relative values Eyes-closed	Delta_Left	39.15	12.24	40.27	11.91	10.19	0.102	0.001
	Delta_Right	39.04	12.23	40.26	11.55	12.29	0.033	0.000
	Theta_Left	18.24	4.19	18.75	3.76	18.94	0.001	0.000
	Theta_Right	18.38	4.09	18.85	3.52	17.58	0.002	0.000
	Alpha_Left	16.28	6.19	16.52	5.90	1.85	1.000	0.174
	Alpha_Right	16.43	6.17	16.62	5.63	1.13	1.000	0.287
	SMR_Left	10.48	3.00	10.41	3.17	0.61	1.000	0.436
	SMR_Right	10.61	3.02	10.63	3.10	0.04	1.000	0.844
	LowBeta_Left	10.39	3.44	10.11	3.47	7.86	0.365	0.005
	LowBeta_Right	10.39	3.38	10.16	3.29	5.98	1.000	0.015
	HighBeta_Left	8.74	4.05	8.20	3.90	21.46	<0.001	0.000
	HighBeta_Right	8.63	3.86	8.10	3.57	24.03	<0.001	0.000
	Gamma_Left	7.20	4.92	6.15	3.66	68.81	<0.001	0.000
	Gamma_Right	7.12	4.88	6.02	3.50	78.23	<0.001	0.000
	Delta_Left	13.49	24.36	12.73	15.02	1.63	1.000	0.202

Absolute values Eyes-open	Delta_Right	14.62	40.40	13.1 2	16.22	2.76	1.000	0.097
	Theta_Left	6.24	10.35	6.01	6.00	0.87	1.000	0.351
	Theta_Right	6.83	19.14	6.16	6.10	2.56	1.000	0.110
	Alpha_Left	3.80	9.20	2.96	4.82	15.33	0.007	0.000
	Alpha_Right	4.14	12.30	3.14	4.90	13.39	0.018	0.000
	SMR_Left	2.37	4.82	2.04	3.82	6.65	0.716	0.010
	SMR_Right	2.70	10.42	2.17	3.76	5.29	1.000	0.022
	LowBeta_Left	2.32	4.68	1.91	3.90	10.83	0.073	0.001
	LowBeta_Right	2.58	8.62	2.01	3.81	8.46	0.262	0.004
	HighBeta_Left	2.23	4.10	1.89	5.09	6.59	0.739	0.010
	HighBeta_Right	2.43	5.98	1.94	4.70	9.40	0.158	0.002
	Gamma_Left	2.09	4.64	1.61	7.41	7.05	0.572	0.008
	Gamma_Right	2.25	5.92	1.63	6.78	10.95	0.068	0.001
Relative values Eyes-open	Delta_Left	43.76	11.27	45.1 6	9.95	20.20	0.001	0.000
	Delta_Right	43.40	11.44	44.8 2	9.87	20.74	<0.001	0.000
	Theta_Left	21.45	5.19	22.5 1	4.71	52.71	<0.001	0.000
	Theta_Right	21.27	5.15	22.4 2	4.54	65.72	<0.001	0.000
	Alpha_Left	11.64	4.38	11.2 4	2.87	13.58	0.017	0.000
	Alpha_Right	11.89	4.43	11.6 3	3.11	5.51	1.000	0.019
	SMR_Left	8.27	2.55	8.11	2.44	4.33	1.000	0.037
	SMR_Right	8.46	2.61	8.37	2.54	1.23	1.000	0.267
	LowBeta_Left	8.10	3.06	7.66	2.88	24.98	<0.001	0.000
	LowBeta_Right	8.24	3.08	7.82	2.82	23.44	<0.001	0.000
	HighBeta_Left	8.25	4.58	7.60	4.46	24.02	<0.001	0.000
	HighBeta_Right	8.33	4.51	7.57	4.22	35.78	<0.001	0.000
	Gamma_Left	6.81	4.96	5.84	4.03	53.51	<0.001	0.000
Gamma_Right	6.86	4.98	5.73	3.79	76.06	<0.001	0.000	
Band-Ratio Eyes-closed	Theta/SMR_Left	2.09	0.90	2.20	0.97	14.57	0.010	0.000
	Theta/SMR_Right	2.08	0.88	2.15	0.90	6.94	0.608	0.008
	Theta/LowBeta_Left	2.11	1.06	2.24	1.15	16.33	0.004	0.000
	Theta/LowBeta_Right	2.12	1.06	2.21	1.07	8.75	0.224	0.003
	Alpha/Theta_Left	1.35	2.15	1.16	1.25	13.73	0.015	0.000
	Alpha/Theta_Right	1.36	2.24	1.14	1.14	18.25	0.001	0.000
	Alpha/LowBeta_Left	1.76	0.66	1.83	0.66	15.49	0.006	0.000
Alpha/LowBeta_Right	1.77	0.65	1.82	0.62	8.95	0.201	0.003	
Band-Ratio Eyes-open	Theta/SMR_Left	1.75	0.78	1.86	0.81	19.70	0.001	0.000
	Theta/SMR_Right	1.72	0.77	1.81	0.78	14.71	0.009	0.000
	Theta/LowBeta_Left	1.91	1.02	2.08	1.10	31.25	<0.001	0.000

Theta/LowBeta_Right	1.86	0.99	2.02	1.04	29.97	<0.001	0.000
Alpha/Theta_Left	0.59	1.05	0.45	0.45	30.57	<0.001	0.000
Alpha/Theta_Right	0.59	0.98	0.47	0.57	26.71	<0.001	0.000
Alpha/LowBeta_Left	0.95	0.33	0.98	0.31	4.72	1.000	0.030
Alpha/LowBeta_Right	0.96	0.33	0.98	0.32	6.19	0.928	0.013

p-values were adjusted by Bonferroni correction

In eyes-closed with absolute values, compared to NCs, patients with ST showed significantly decreased EEGs in Alpha_Right ($p=0.029$), LowBeta_Right ($p=0.015$), Gamma_Left ($p=0.032$), and Gamma_Right ($p=0.008$). In eyes-closed with relative values, patients showed increased EEGs in Delta_Right ($p=0.033$), Theta_Left ($p=0.001$), and Theta_Right ($p=0.002$). Patients showed also increased EEGs in HighBeta_Left ($p<0.001$), HighBeta_Right ($p<0.001$), Gamma_Left ($p<0.001$), and Gamma_Right ($p<0.001$).

In eyes-open with absolute values, patients showed decreased EEGs in Alpha_Left ($p=0.007$) and Alpha_Right ($p=0.018$). In eyes-open with relative values, patients showed increased EEGs in Delta_Left ($p=0.001$), Delta_Right ($p<0.001$), Theta_Left ($p<0.001$), and Theta_Right ($p<0.001$). Patients showed also decreased EEGs in Alpha_Left ($p=0.017$), LowBeta_Left ($p<0.001$), LowBeta_Right ($p<0.001$), HighBeta_Left ($p<0.001$), HighBeta_Right ($p<0.001$), Gamma_Left ($p<0.001$), and Gamma_Right ($p<0.001$).

In eyes-closed with Band-Ratio, patients showed increased EEGs in Theta/SMR_Left ($p=0.010$), Theta/LowBeta_Left ($p=0.004$), and Alpha/LowBeta_Left ($p=0.006$). Patients showed decreased EEGs in Alpha/Theta_Left ($p=0.015$) and Alpha/Theta_Right ($p=0.001$).

In eyes-open with Band-Ratio, patients showed increased EEGs in Theta/SMR_Left ($p=0.001$), Theta/SMR_Right ($p=0.009$), Theta/LowBeta_Left ($p<0.001$), and Theta/LowBeta_Right ($p<0.001$). Patients showed reduced EEGs in Alpha/Theta_Left ($p<0.001$) and Alpha/Theta_Right ($p<0.001$).

In classification model, SVM showed the highest balanced accuracy of 0.59 with the accumulated combination of 14 features selected, compared to GBM (Table 2).

Table 2. Classification Model's Performance.

Index	SVM	GBM
Balanced Accuracy	0.59	0.56
Sensitivity	0.66	0.63
Specificity	0.52	0.5
F1-score	0.61	0.59
Precision	0.57	0.55
AUC-ROC	0.63	0.59

The selected features were absolute with eyes-closed Delta_Left, Delta_Right, SMR_Right, LowBeta_Left, relative with eyes-closed Delta_Left, LowBeta_Left, LowBeta_Right, relative with eyes-open SMR_Right, Band-Ratio with eyes-closed Theta/LowBeta_Right, Alpha/Theta_Right, Alpha/LowBeta_Left, Alpha/LowBeta_Right, Band-Ratio with eyes-open Theta/SMR_Right, and Theta/LowBeta_Right (Table 3).

Table 3. Features selected and ranked by RFECV-SVM.

Rank	Features selected		f	Adjusted p	Original p
1	Absolute_CE	Delta_Left	0.26	1.000	0.610
2		Delta_Right	1.26	1.000	0.261
3		SMR_Right	7.26	0.509	0.007
4		LowBeta_Left	10.56	0.084	0.001
5	Relative_CE	Delta_Left	10.19	0.102	0.001
6		LowBeta_Left	7.86	0.365	0.005
7		LowBeta_Right	5.98	1.000	0.015
8	Relative_OE	SMR_Right	1.23	1.000	0.267
9	Band-Ratio_CE	Theta/LowBeta_Right	8.75	0.224	0.003
10		Alpha/Theta_Right	18.25	0.001	0.000
11		Alpha/LowBeta_Left	15.49	0.006	0.000
12		Alpha/LowBeta_Right	8.95	0.201	0.003
13	Band-Ratio_OE	Theta/SMR_Right	14.71	0.009	0.000
14		Theta/LowBeta_Right	29.97	<0.001	0.000

CE, Eyes-closed; OE, Eyes-open

Discussion

This study investigated 2-channel EEG biomarkers and an ML classification model to differentiate patients with ST and NCs. In ANOVA, several band frequencies were compared between patients and NCs. Overall, in patients with ST, the power of slow-frequency bands (Delta and Theta) was increased, whereas that of middle- and fast-frequency bands was decreased. The abnormal increase in delta and theta power may be related to changes in neural plasticity that compensate for deficient auditory input with thalamocortical dysrhythmia^{26,27}. However, another study showed increased resting-state beta activity in 8 patients with chronic tinnitus compared to 15 NCs²⁷. This inconsistency makes it difficult to generalize our results, although that study had a much smaller sample size compared to ours. Additionally, thalamocortical dysfunction, including projections to the prefrontal cortex, may be related to the prevalence of tinnitus in patients with chronic pain²⁸. Therefore, Abnormal increase in delta and theta activity during resting state have been associated with compensatory mechanism following deficiency in auditory nerve system. Thalamocortical circuits are considered to play a key role in this process. In our results, although the EEG recordings were focused on frontal regions, an increase in relative power within these low-frequency bands was also observed in tinnitus patients. It appears to reflect a weakening of thalamic inhibitory control due to impaired afferent auditory input. The absence of external sensory stimuli may facilitate the emergence of slow-frequency of thalamocortical rhythms. This rhythmic activity could be interpreted as a compensatory attempt by the brain to accommodate with sensory input disruption. Nevertheless, these compensatory mechanisms may fail to prevent the propagation of aberrant signals to the auditory cortex, ultimately resulting in the conscious perception of tinnitus.

In the ML classification model, the best performance was 59% using SVM. However, this accuracy was not sufficient to effectively classify patients with ST and NCs. A previous study reported the highest EEG classification accuracy of 96% and 94% using SVM in a dataset of 129 patients with tinnitus and 142 healthy individuals²⁹. In that study, the selected 23 EEG features included absolute Delta, Theta, HighBeta, Gamma, and relative Alpha bands. A few studies have reported reasonable accuracy in EEG classification models. However, the sample sizes in those studies were relatively small ($n = 100\text{--}200$)^{30,31}.

A study that enrolled 20 patients with ST found that those with low-frequency ST (frequency < 4,000 Hz) exhibited increased Gamma activity in posterior cingulate cortex

compared to controls. Additionally, compared to controls, decreased Alpha power in angular gyrus and auditory association cortex was observed in patients with high-frequency ST (frequency $\geq 4,000$ Hz)³². These findings suggest that while EEG-based ML models have potential in classifying ST and NCs, further research is needed to improve classification accuracy. Future studies should focus on increasing sample sizes, refining feature selection techniques, and optimizing ML models to enhance classification performance and reproducibility.

Conclusions

An important issue in EEG-based tinnitus classification is the inconsistency in reported frequency features across studies, which needs to be addressed for more reliable results. Variations in data preprocessing, feature selection, and model implementation contribute to this issue, making it difficult to establish standardized biomarkers. Additionally, small sample sizes in many studies limit generalizability and may lead to inconsistent classification performance. To improve accuracy and robustness, future research should focus on larger datasets, optimized feature selection strategies, and the application of more advanced ML models in patients with specific subtypes of tinnitus. Furthermore, integrating EEG with other physiological or clinical measures may enhance classification reliability. Advancing these methods could contribute to the development of objective, EEG-based diagnostic tools for tinnitus.

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